

Project¹ Number: 101067882

Project Acronym: PACGEL

Project title: Plasma-Activated hydroGel: new frontiers in cardiac regenerative medicine

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

¹ The term ‘project’ used in this template equates to an ‘action’ in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

1. Data Summary

The objective of PACGEL project is to exploit tailored reactive oxygen species (ROS) doses, generated by an atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ), to design ROS-releasing hydrogels, used as either injectable systems for cardiac regenerative medicine or *in vitro* models of human cardiac diseases. One of the relevant tasks within this objective is to quantify the relevant ROS doses generated by APPJ device, tuning device parameters and conditions of treatments (type of media, their volume and surface area, APPJ distance and time of treatment), and to evaluate their effects on different cardiac cell types (in terms of cell viability and protein expression). Afterwards, selected ROS doses will be generated into hydrogels (to be used either as injectable systems or bioprinted constructs) to induce specific cell responses (*i.e.*, cardioprotection or oxidative stresses, respectively).

To this aim, existing data such as experimental protocols from scientific literature will be adapted and optimized to fit the needs of the project (*e.g.*, ROS quantification in liquids, polymer solutions, hydrogels and cells). The collected experimental data on ROS doses generated under different APPJ treatment conditions are crucial for the project and within the *Plasma Medicine* scientific community. Indeed, there is no database available for data comparison, able to facilitate ROS tuning to get a certain biological effect. Data obtained from PACGEL will be mainly exploited for publications (scientific articles and conference presentations) and will be collected as an internal database elucidating the effect of ROS doses (generated under different conditions) on various cells. As the project is at its early stage, more data need to be collected before deposit and sharing them through a repository platform (protected under a creative common CC-by-NC license).

During the course of the project, several types and formats of data will be generated, including:

- digital format, collected in Excel files (.xlsx), from experimental measurements
- images in .png and .tiff format of physical samples
- experimental protocols and reports in .pdf and .doc format

Some of the data (numerical values derived from experiments) will be collected by manual annotation in my personal lab-book and, then, transferred into Excel files in my laptop. Image files, taken by microscope or other cameras, will be transferred into my lap-top and saved into .png or .tiff format. Protocols and reports will be collected as Word files and final version saved in .pdf. Each generated dataset will be named accordingly (name of the experiment, page number of the lab-book, date, my initials and version number). These data will be stored in a proper folder (*i.e.*, a dedicated folder collecting experiment results into distinct folders for each specific experiment type) in a computer (generally my lap-top) protected by a password. A copy of the data will be stored in Cloud (*e.g.*, Dropbox and OneDrive) by weekly updates as a backup. Moreover, once a set of experiment is finished, all the generated data will be deposited in a trustworthy depository (*e.g.*, Zenodo) protected with embargo through my personal account, thus ensuring maximal data protection and security.

Regarding my collected experimental data (*e.g.*, ROS concentrations from quantitative measurements and microscope images) and optimized and adapted protocols from literature, they will be adapted in a suitable format for publication purposes during the second project year. In the early project phase, all data generated, if not published, will serve as a database for internal

use within the course of the project. A patent anteriority search will be performed to assess the possibility of patent submission, before sharing any crucial information.

In case of re-use of any external data, permission from copyright owners will be asked. Moreover, during the course of the project, some existing data from the scientific literature will be re-used, such as, for example, experimental protocols, that will be optimized and/or adapted to the project needs. In more details, the general protocols available in the scientific literature for ROS quantification in liquids will be adapted and optimized for polymer solutions and hydrogels. Existing protocols for polymer synthesis and hydrogel formulations will be also re-used, by citing previous publications while highlighting any protocol modification. Regarding the available experimental data from the literature, they will serve for comparison during the experimental work, enabling a validation of the results, obtained using the same experimental conditions.

The collected data during the course of the project will be mainly manually acquired from:

- experimental results (by manual collection of the obtained results, then ordinated in excel files before graphics plotting)
- collected images of physical samples (through microscope or other cameras)
- creation of protocols, from my manual annotation in my lab-book

Regarding the re-used existing data from the literature (*e.g.*, experimental protocols), they will be extracted from published articles (with proper source citation while highlighting any deviation).

At this early stage of the project, I estimate to generate around 10 GB, that may vary following the evolution of the project up to 50 GB.

All data generated in PACGEL from experimental measurements will serve as an internal database within the Host Institution research group, shareable, upon request, by email or web free service for transferring big data volumes (*e.g.*, by WeTransfer). During the project, the generated data will be exploited for publications and disseminations (*i.e.*, by scientific articles, poster and oral presentations in conferences, respectively). Publications will be available open access (OA) as well as their relative publication data, stored in an online data repository (*e.g.*, Zenodo). Upon completion of the project, non-published and non-confidential data, deposited in Zenodo too, and protected via embargo policy, will be made OA available by the end of the project (at the latest 4 years later), thus all the scientific community will have free access and will be able to use them (under proper citation of the source).

2. FAIR data

2. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

I will store my generated data into a free and trustworthy depository (*e.g.*, Zenodo) which generates a DOI for each stored data. Thus, I am ensuring once I will make them OA available, they will be linked to a unique identifier (DOI), making them identifiable and locatable through a unique and standard identification mechanism for further re-use by other parties under proper source citation.

I will name those stored data files (*i.e.*, experimental protocols (.pdf), collected data from experiments (.xlsx), and the images (.png or .tiff)) according to the type and year of the performed experiment, followed by my initials (*e.g.*, “ROS quantification_2023_IH”). Also, a version number will be also clearly indicated in the file name (*e.g.*, “ROS quantification_2023_IH_version_1”) in case of updates.

I will ensure that my stored data are findable through defined relevant keywords (*e.g.*, ROS, H₂O₂, NO₂, plasma jet) according to the experiment performed and related results generated.

The deposited data will be provided with their own metadata which includes:

- file name
- short description
- keywords
- DOI
- date of creation
- version number
- size of the file
- creator/ownership
- modification abilities/data protection

More details will be found once the file is opened (title of the experiment, brief description of the objective, protocol description and any deviation, results with raw and analyzed data, as well as proper information on the project related to these data).

2.2. Making data openly accessible

For security reasons and as an additional backup, I will store all my generated data (*e.g.*, excel files with raw and processed data, experimental protocols and images) in Zenodo depository during the course of the project (with updates after the end of each experimental set, according to the defined WPs). Since the generated data from experimental work are ‘living data’ and not final data generated, modifications as well as improvements (*i.e.*, in protocols and derived results) will probably be done during the course of the project (*i.e.*, generating new versions of the data), thus, I will preserve them under embargo protection. New and final version of data will be introduced once a set of experiments finished and updated when needed with new data following the experimental workflow performed. These generated data are first aimed for patent and publications purposes. Identified Intellectual Property (IP) sensitive data will not be shared for patenting reasons and will remain protected under embargo. After a careful analysis of patenting opportunities, data that cannot be patented will be used for publications. Once these data published in scientific articles (in OA journals), I will update the privacy of the corresponding folder in Zenodo and make the data related to the published publication OA available at the latest of the publication date. Data not used in publications or patents, will be

made OA available by the end of the project (at the latest up to 4 years by the end of the project, according to the GA).

The data will be provided in an accessible way and I will ensure that they are readable through available and free software (*i.e.*, Excel, Acrobat Reader, Power Point or Word files). In the improbable case that any specific software is needed to open some of the shared data, the type of software will be clearly indicated and instructions for opening and treating the files will be provided. It is not expected that specific software will be needed to read the deposited data, but in the case that some data need a specific software for their access and analysis, I will ensure to provide it in an open-source code with the specific instructions and documentation to access the data.

I will store my data, as well as associated metadata and the needed documentation/instructions into Zenodo, a certified and trustworthy data depository for free, which provides a DOI to the stored files, as well as allowing the storage option from open to embargoed.

Zenodo repository have the possibility to store any type of data (up to 50 GB per file) with a large choice of privacy content (upon online free registration). Options to choose the access to the stored data from open to embargoed and updates of the deposited data can be done at any time too, as well as changes in privacy content. Zenodo repository can be used as a personal repository (for data storage under embargo), and as a platform for data sharing as it offers the possibility to generate a DOI to the stored data, thus making them available and sharable with external users.

Zenodo is an online free depository and did not present any restrictions on use. The repository is accessible even without proper authentication. Registration and free account creation is mandatory for the storage of data.

Zenodo is hosted at the CERN and managed by several highly-qualified staff members ensuring the storage and the security of the stored data under strict rules. Data that are not appropriate or with missing metadata information can be removed from the depository as out of the scope leading to a DOI revocation.

Zenodo depository is accessible online through any computer or device equipped with a screen and internet connection.

All external users can have access to the files in Zenodo repository without proper online identification (only for OA content). Since PACGEL project is at his early stage, and it is not yet predicted that some data will be used for patenting reasons, I will ensure the full OA to my stored data only after a careful analysis of patenting opportunities.

2.3. Making data interoperable

One of the aims of the project is to collect data for comparison with results already available in the literature, thus creating a wider a database in the field. To do so, the data will be organized in the same format of already published and available data from literature. The data will be organized in Excel files (including a first sheet with all the relevant information and instructions; replica of the data will be provided ordered in different sheet, facilitating consulting and reuse). Experimental protocols will be provided in PDF format.

I will take care to employ the same vocabulary, keywords and annotations already used within the scientific community in the field and defined in literature in order to ensure the

interoperability of data generated in the project. In case of specific deviation, I will provide a list of abbreviations and definitions as well as all the relevant information, and the vocabulary employed for the interpretation of data, in the first description sheet.

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Non-IP sensitive data will be made available after manuscript publication with no embargo and will be licensed through CC-by-NC license, thus ensuring their re-use (through Zenodo repositories). The produced data could be re-used for non-commercial reasons by third parties, under proper citation of the used data (through the DOI).

All my generated data will be stored with embargo into Zenodo repository and updated within the course of the project as they are living data. IP-sensitive data will remain protected under embargo for patenting reasons. Non-IP sensitive data used for publications purposes will be made permanently OA at the latest of the publication date. Other non-IP and non-published stored data, will be made permanently OA only by the end of the project, at the latest up to 4 years by the end of the project (in case of late publications after the end of the project, as stated in the GA).

Once the stored data made OA available, they will be ready to use by third parties upon adequate citation source (*i.e.*, DOI). Since I will provide a permanent OA to the stored data by the end of the project (except those selected as IP-sensitive data), they will be usable after the end of the project (upon proper source citation).

Moreover, since my generated and stored data are living data and during their lifecycle, some generated data may be obsolete or irrelevant following the evolution of the project. Thus, by updating new versions of the data, I will clearly highlight the changes in data removal or cleaning by providing a clear explanation (in a separate excel sheet, or by adding comments or footnotes on PDF documents). In that way, my data quality assurance process can be easily followed by anyone who is interested in re-using the data (once OA available).

3. Allocation of resources

In this early project phase, there are no costs related to project data management (since no big data have been generated so far). As soon as data are generated and ready to store, I will use free repositories, such as Zenodo. Data files will be prepared by myself and checked by my supervisor, free Clouds (*e.g.*, Dropbox and OneDrive) will be used to store data, together with personal laptop, as well as pen drives and an external hard disk. Hence, I do not foresee costs for data management, except for the acquisition of an external hard disk. In case of changes, I will update this plan accordingly.

In case of the management and storage of my generated data generates additional costs, they will be covered through the budget allocated to the project, as a part of project management (corresponding to the WP5).

I am responsible of PACGEL data management, jointly with my supervisor. Since the project is at its early stage and not enough data have been generated, in the next months, we will jointly decide the resources for long-term data preservation.

4. Data security

Currently, data are stored in a computer (my laptop) protected by a password, and a version is also stored in clouds (*i.e.*, PACGEL folders in POLITO OneDrive and Dropbox) and in personal USB pens. An external hard disk (of a few TB capacity) will be acquired in the project to store all generated data. The supervisor is acquiring a new computer, where additionally PACGEL folder will be stored. The computer will be protected by a password.

For a safe long-term preservation of data, I will exploit certified repositories, such as Zenodo.

5. Ethical aspects

Not applicable. The project does not involve ethical issues regarding data management.

6. Other issues

My data management plan includes the storage of data in the institutional server provided by my Host Institution. I will follow any new instructions from my institution.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	06.11.2023	▪ Initial version_Month 6